

As soon as panicles began to emerge, the plants were covered with cloth screens to provide 22-26% of full sunlight for 28 d. Check plants were grown in full daylight. The experiment was in a randomized complete block

with six replications.

Grain yield in all varieties decreased significantly with low light exposure (see table). Hashikalmi was least affected, followed by BR9 and Kataktara. BR9 had the highest yields at

both light intensities, and was the least affected modern variety. The highest yield reduction was in BR6, followed by BRI. Filled spikelets were more affected than 1,000-grain weight. □

Effect of low light intensity at ripening on yield and 2 yield components of aus varieties.^aBRRI, Bangladesh.

Variety	Grain yield			Filled spikelets			1000-grain weight		
	Normal light (g/pot)	Low light (g/pot)	Reduction (%) due to low light	Normal light (%)	Low light (%)	Reduction (%) due to low light	Normal light (g)	Low light (g)	Reduction (%) due to low light
BR1	10.98 g	3.96 ef	64 e	73 cd	47 d	36 cd	19.89 e	16.50 g	17 cd
BR3	25.24 b	10.74 b	57 de	81 abc	52 cd	35 cd	25.64 ab	21.91 ab	15 bc
BR6	14.73 f	3.47 f	76 f	85 ab	48 d	44 de	23.82 c	20.03 de	19 d
BR9	31.81 a	17.19 a	46 b	77 bc	56 bcd	26 bc	21.64 d	20.55 cd	5 a
BR12	18.69 de	7.73 ce	58 de	90 a	65 b	28 bc	20.98 de	17.42 fg	17 cd
Hashikalmi	17.14 ef	11.93 b	30 a	90 a	80 a	11 a	24.56 bc	23.03 a	6 a
Dharail	16.37 e	6.45 de	61 de	69 d	32 e	52 a	23.65 c	21.76 bc	7 a
Morichboti	21.23 cd	9.30 bc	56 cde	83 ab	54 cd	34 bcd	26.33 a	23.21 a	13 b
Dular	24.31 b	12.04 b	51 bed	82 ab	57 bc	30 bc	23.50 c	21.99 ab	14 bc
Kataktara	22.43 bc	11.63 b	48 b	83 ab	65 b	22 ab	21.82 d	19.12 e	12 b

^aIn a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level (DMRT). Within a variety, treatment effect was significant at the % level (DMRT).

Correlations between allogamic and agronomic traits in rice

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We studied the correlations between allogamic and agronomic traits in F3-derived lines from the BC2 generation of the cross *Oryza sativa* L. / *Oryza longistaminata* A. Chev. The male parent possesses well-developed floral parts. The F3 lines were evaluated in a completely randomized block design with four replications at two locations in 1986-87.

Allogamic traits evaluated were stigma and anther length, agronomic characters were spikelet and panicle length. Variance and covariance analyses were used.

Table 1 shows the very high coefficients of heritability found for stigma, anther, and spikelet length (0.92, 0.94, and 0.92, respectively). These results indicate that visual selection can be used efficiently for these traits.

Table 1. Coefficient of heritability and average length of stigma, anther, spikelet, and panicle.

Trait	Coefficient of heritability	Average length
Stigma length (mm)	0.9163	1.53 ± 0.27
Anther length (mm)	0.9413	2.62 ± 0.33
Spikelet length (mm)	0.9215	7.39 ± 0.50
Panicle length (cm)	0.6389	19.11 ± 2.81

Table 2. Genetic (G), phenotypic (P), and environmental (E) correlations between stigma, anther, spikelet, and panicle length.

		Anther	Spikelet	Panicle
Stigma	G	0.5548**	0.1565	0.0900
	P	0.5138**	0.1393	0.0349
	E	0.2980	0.1614*	0.2278
Anther	G		-0.0280	0.1979
	P		-0.0076	0.1881
	E		0.2020	0.1231
Spikelet	G			-0.3006
	P			-0.1336
	E			0.3785

Table 2 shows significant and positive genetic and phenotypic correlations between the allogamic characters, indicating that selection for one character can positively change the other.

No significant correlations were found between the two allogamic traits and spikelet and panicle length. □

Screening long-duration rice cultivars for ratooning ability

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We screened 210 entries from IRTP nurseries (1986 International Rice Shallow Water Observational Nurseries [IRSWON], 1986 International Rice Deepwater Observational Nurseries [IRDWON], and 1985 International Upland Rice Yield Nurseries [IURYN]) to select semidwarf long-duration or photoperiod-sensitive rice cultivars that, when sown in November, could be harvested in April/ May with a ratoon crop flowering in late Sep.

Entries were sown 28 Nov 1986 and transplanted 16 Jan 1987 in 2 rows at